

THERMAL STRESS ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED AXISYMMETRIC SOLIDS

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This paper presents a finite element formulation for the prediction of temperature fields induced in laminated composite solids of axisymmetric geometry by external heat sources. Formulation for the associated thermal stresses and deformation in the structure is also derived. The computational algorithm corresponding to these formulations have been incorporated in an existing computer code, TEPASAC developed by the author (TRH) for structures of homogeneous materials. Although the formulation is derived primarily for laminated composite materials of axisymmetric geometry, it can also be used for structures of plane geometries as a degenerated axisymmetric geometry by adding an artificial large value to the radial dimensions.

A numerical example involves a nose cone subjected to a steady-state heat influx from the outside surface. The inner surface of the cone is kept at 0°C at all times. There are 24 graphite-epoxy lamina in the cone.

The following material properties were used in the computations:

Young's moduli, GPa: $E_1=147$; $E_2=9.1$; $E_3=0.03$,

Shear moduli, GPa: $G_{12}=4.27$; $G_{13}=4.69$; $G_{23}=5.93$

Poisson's ratios: $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.3$; $\nu_{23}=0.49$

Linear thermal expansion coefficients/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$:

$$\alpha_1 = -7.7 \times 10^{-8}; \quad \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = 33.7 \times 10^{-6}$$

Thermal conductivities, $\text{W}/\text{mm}^{\circ}\text{C}$:

$$k_1=0.08; \quad k_2=k_3=0.008$$

The temperature fields in the cone with various fiber orientations and stacking sequences resulting from the imposition of above thermal boundary conditions are examined. The following two observations on the numerical results can be made:

(1) The temperature distribution is considerably more uniform in the case of fibers orienting along the axial direction. The other extreme, of course, is the case in which all fibers orient normal to the axis of the cone;

(2) For the equal number of plies and fiber orientations, the stackings which have fibers aligned axially near outer surfaces, e.g. $(0^{\circ}_{12}/90^{\circ}_{12})$ have lower peak temperature and temperature gradients than the cases otherwise.

It is not surprising that modest thermal stresses exist in the cases in which more

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fibers are oriented along the axial direction. The fiber orientation and stacking sequence indeed play important roles in the distribution of both temperature and thermal stresses in the structure.

Strong influence of stacking sequence on stress distribution is a well-known fact. However, this influence appears even more critical in the derivation of thermal stresses. This factor will thus become an important aspect in the design analysis of laminated composite structures subject to thermal loads.